

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

INTERACTION OF NIKEL ATOMS WITH GROUP VI IMPURITIES IN THE SILICON LATTICE

Bakhadir Khanov M.,

Tashkent State Technical University,
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Iliev X.,

Tashkent State Technical University,
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Tursunov M.,

Termez State University,
Termez, Uzbekistan

Karshiyev Sh.

Tashkent State Technical University,
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Abstract

The results of the study of silicon alloyed with Ni and Se atoms are given. The introduction of nickel was carried out by dusting the silicon surface and then by “low temperature” diffusion for 0.5 h at $T = 1150^\circ\text{C}$. Additional heat treatment of Ni and Se alloyed samples was performed in the same way ($T = 820^\circ\text{C}$, for 0.5 hours). The composition of the samples was studied using SEM. The change in the properties of Si <Ni, Se> is explained by the formation of binary complexes of nickel and selenium atoms in the crystal lattice of silicon.

Keywords: binary complex, nickel, selenium, open circuit voltage, short circuit current.

INTRODUCTION

Silicon remains the main material for modern electronics. The introduction of an electroneutral molecule or complex objects containing introductory atoms of various elements into a silicon lattice leads to the detection of new effects [1]. This paper presents the results of studies of solar cells based on silicon added with Ni and Se atoms. We know that thermal and radiation defects in silicon are mainly determined by the optically active oxygen concentration. Because the control of such oxygen concentration creates a great technological opportunity, the study of nickel and oxygen segregation processes is important. This is because nickel atoms in

silicon have a sufficiently high solubility $N \sim 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and they are in the electroneutral state [2].

The starting material was monocrystalline silicon obtained by the Chokhralsky method with specific resistance p-type $\rho = 0,5 \text{ Ohm}\cdot\text{cm}$, and n-type $\rho = 100 \text{ Ohm}\cdot\text{cm}$. In these samples, the optically active oxygen concentration is $N_{\text{O}_2} = (5 \div 6) \cdot 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The sample size is $1 \times 4 \times 0,8 \text{ mm}^3$.

All samples were mechanically and chemically treated under the same conditions. The electrical parameters of the samples were determined using the Hall effect. The contact part of the samples was coated with nickel with a chemical hypophosphite solution.

Table 1.

The average value of the initial samples is the electrical and optical parameters.

Source material	Conductivity type	ρ	μ	$p, n \text{ cm}^{-3}$
KDB-0,5	p	0,5	329	$4 \cdot 10^{16}$
KEF-100	n	97	1340	$4,8 \cdot 10^{13}$

THE EXPERIMENTALLY PART

Diffusion of nickel atoms was carried out at $T = 1150^\circ\text{C}$ for $t = 30$ minutes in quartz ampoules using the “low temperature stepwise” diffusion method. Diffusion of the Se atoms was then performed at $t = 1200^\circ\text{C}$ for $t = 30$ min. As a result, p-n-shaped structures, ie photocells, were obtained. Given the relatively high binding energy in the NiSe molecule and the high diffusion coefficient of nickel, the additional heat treatment temperature was selected at $T = 820^\circ\text{C}$. After additional heat treatment, the photocell (SC) voltage was measured and the short-circuit current density (J_{sc}) was measured. In Si <B, Ni, Se> photocells, the J_{sc} value

increased by 22% compared to Si <B, Se> (SC), while the U_{oc} value increased from 427 mV to 480 mV, ie by 12% (Table 2). The increase in the parameters of (SC)s after heat treatment Si <B, Se> was explained by the hetering of selenium atoms to recombination in silicon [3-4]. After the diffusion process, such properties of selenium atoms are almost non-existent, as they do not have time to become electroactive due to rapid cooling after diffusion. Long-term additional heat treatment activates the formation of complexes, which has led to uncontrolled intrusions and heterogeneity of point defects.

Table 2.

Electrophysical parameters of solar cells after additional heat treatment at a temperature of $T = 820\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Samples	J_{sc} , mA/cm ²	U_{oc} , mV	P_{max} , mW/cm ²
Si<B, Se>	18	427	7,686
Si<B, Ni, Se>	22	480	10,560
Si<B, Ni, Se> settings SC Si<B, Se> change in relation to SC	+22%	+12 %	+37.4%

Thus, the technologically optimal conditions for the formation of complexes of the Si_2NiSe type were determined - the diffusion temperature of selenium and nickel input atoms was $T = 1160\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the temperature of

additional heat treatment (complex formation) was $T = 820\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. After diffusion and additional heat treatment, it was found that SC parameters increased by $U_{oc} - 12\%$, $J_{sc} - 22\%$, $P_{max} - 37.4\%$ [5-6].

Figure 1. Composition of complexes of nickel and selenium atoms (SEM) formed in silicon after diffusion.

Figure 2. Possible options for the formation of nickel-selenium complexes in the silicon lattice. a) - in adjacent nodes of the silicon lattice, b) - in the interstices of the silicon lattice.

CONCLUSION

After the experiments, we determined the composition of the sample using an electron microscope (Figure 1.). The results showed that the amount of nickel and selenium atoms in silicon was the same. This indicates that nickel and selenium atoms in silicon combine to form binary complexes. The results of the increase in silicon salinity $U_{oc} - 12\%$, short-circuit current $J_{sc} - 22\%$, power $P_{max} - 37.4\%$ also confirm the results. The new materials that is Si enriched with binary cells of $\text{Si}_2\text{B}_{VI}^{++}\text{Ni}^{-}$ type allows us create on one's base the new optoelectronic and nano electronic devices and also high effective photo elements based Si having same the

best parameters than expensive many cascade photo elements based A^{III}B^V (Figure 2). That what is the new scientific branch which requires carry out the complex experimental and theoretical investigations [7-8].

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interests.

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